

IR58025 A showed the highest mean outcrossing rate, 16.67% (see table). Individual combinations with high outcrossings were IR58025 A/ IR29723-143-3-2-1, IR58025 A/ IR24, and V20 A/ IR29723-143-3-2-1. Maximum anther

length and breadth were found in IR54742-22-19-3. High filament length and pollen diameter was recorded for IR29723-143-3-2-1; V20 A showed lengthy stigma; and IR58025 A had high stigma exertion and ovary

breadth. Except for stigma exertion, none of the varieties were linked closely with outcrossing rate. The lines IR58025 A, IR29723-143-3-2-1, and IR54742-22-19-3 can be well utilized for hybrid rice improvement. ■

Outcrossing rate in some hybrid varieties and its relationship with floral traits. Tamil Nadu, India.

Cross ^a	Filament length (mm)	Anther length (mm)	Anther breadth (mm)	Pollen diameter (mm)	Style length (mm)	Stigma length (mm)	Ovary length (mm)	Ovary breadth (mm)	SE (%)	Outcrossing rate (%)
L1/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	18.18
L1/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	13.13
L1/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	18.91
L1/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	15.90
L1/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	15.74
Mean										16.37
L2/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	12.21
L2/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	16.09
L2/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	18.29
L2/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	10.41
L2/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	9.53
Mean										13.31
L3/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	19.00
L3/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	16.78
L3/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	20.91
L3/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	9.98
L3/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	16.68
Mean										16.67
L4/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	2.29
L4/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	1.28
L4/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	11.94
L4/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	5.66
L4/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	12.01
Mean										6.64
CD										0.40
r	0.18	-0.12	0.24	0.40	0.38	0.01	-0.35	0.20	0.69 ^b	

^a L1 = V20A, L2 = Zs97 A, L3 = IR58025 A, L4 = IR62829 A, T1 = IR24, T2 = IR54742-22-19-3, T3 = IR29723-143-3-2-1, T4 = IR976-19-1, T5 = ARC11353. ^b Significant at 5% level.

Parag 401, a semidwarf rice variety developed through anther culture

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Parag 401 is derived from a cross between Prabhavati and Basmati 370. Anthers coming from the F₁ plants were cultivated to produce doubled haploid plants. Morphology of 70 haplodiploid progenies was studied, and based on yield-related characteristics, selected genotypes were evaluated in multilocation experiments from 1993 to 1996.

Grain quality characteristics of ACR401 compared with selected varieties. Maharashtra, India, 1993-96^a

Character	ACR401 (Parag 401)	Prabhavati	Sugandha	Basmati 370
Plant height (cm)	71.0	75.0	44.0	85.0
Maturity (d)	110	120	116	128
Iron chlorosis reaction	T	T	T	S
Grain yield ^a (t ha ⁻¹)	3.6	3.2	3.3	1.4
Grain type	LS	MS	LS	LS
L/B	4.02	3.20	3.93	4.07
Kernel elongation after cooking	1.53	1.17	1.33	2.00
Gelatinization temperature	I	L	L	I
Protein content(%)	8.30	7.0	8.33	8.40

^a LS = long slender, MS = medium slender, T = tolerant, S = sensitive, L = low, I = intermediate. Av 3 yr.

One of the selections, ACR401 (anther culture rice), showed superior quality characters over the check variety Prabhavati with a similar yield (see table). ACR 401 is resistant to iron chlorosis and has slender grains, high grain length-grain breadth ratio (L/B),

higher kernel elongation after cooking, intermediate amylose content, and scented grains. The genotype ACR 401 has been officially released as Parag 401 for cultivation as an irrigated rice for Vertisols of Maharashtra State. ■